

INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INNOVATION AND INTEGRATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19567683>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 10th April 2026

Accepted: 11th April 2026

Online: 13th April 2026

KEYWORDS

primary education, innovation, integration, interdisciplinarity, modern pedagogy, educational efficiency, interactive methods, educational process, creative thinking, pedagogical technologies

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the interdependence of innovative approaches and interdisciplinary integration in the process of primary school education. The introduction of innovations in the modern education system serves as an important factor in the development of independent thinking of students, improvement of lesson efficiency, and deep assimilation of knowledge. At the same time, through interdisciplinary integration, students develop the skills to create a holistic vision and understand the connection between different disciplines. The article reveals the importance of the combination of these two approaches in improving the quality of primary education and gives practical recommendations.

Introduction

The primary education system is currently undergoing a period of fundamental changes. The rapid development of modern society, the sharp increase in the flow of information and

the need for new knowledge require new approaches to the educational process. In this regard, the concepts of innovation and integration play an important role in primary school education, helping to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Innovation is the introduction of new ideas, methods and technologies into the educational process, while integration is aimed at forming holistic knowledge and skills in students by ensuring the connection between different subjects. These two concepts are closely related and, when used together, allow developing the thinking of primary school students, forming independent thinking and connecting knowledge with life.

This article discusses the interrelation of innovation and integration in primary school education, their impact on the quality of education and the possibilities of practical application. It also analyzes the importance and effectiveness of organizing integrated lessons based on innovative approaches.

Although the concepts of innovation and integration in primary school education can be considered separately, in the practical process they are manifested in an inextricable relationship. Because in organizing a modern lesson, not only the use of new pedagogical technologies, but also the harmonization of educational materials with each other is of great importance.

First of all, an innovative approach brings a new spirit to the primary education process. While in traditional lessons the teacher is the main source of information, through innovative methods the student becomes an active subject. For example, interactive methods, the use of information and communication technologies, game technologies and problem-based teaching increase students' interest in the lesson. This, in turn, contributes to the solid assimilation of knowledge.

Integration forms the ability of students to understand the world as a whole. For primary school students, sharply separating individual subjects sometimes complicates their understanding process. Therefore, studying the same topic from different perspectives by ensuring intersubject connections gives more effective results. For example, connecting the text read in a native language lesson with environmental lessons or explaining mathematics problems based on everyday life situations deepens students' knowledge.

The interrelationship of innovation and integration is clearly visible at this point. That is, innovative methods allow for the effective organization of integrated lessons. For example, multimedia tools can be used to deliver lessons that cover multiple subject areas at once. Such lessons encourage students to be active, develop their independent thinking skills, and help them connect knowledge with practice.

Integrated lessons are also an important tool for developing creativity and logical thinking in students. In such lessons, organized on the basis of innovative approaches, students not only receive ready-made knowledge, but also analyze, compare and generalize it. As a result, they acquire important competencies such as the ability to freely express their thoughts and find solutions to problem situations.

In addition, the combination of innovation and integration in primary education requires a high level of professional skills from the teacher. When planning a lesson, the teacher must take into account the age characteristics, interests and individual capabilities of

students. At the same time, it is important to master modern pedagogical technologies and be able to correctly apply them in practice.

In primary school education, innovation and integration are important factors that complement each other and increase the effectiveness of education. By using them in harmony, it is possible to strengthen students' motivation to learn, develop independent thinking, and take the quality of education to a new level.

In conclusion, innovation and integration are closely related in primary school education, and they play an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Through innovative approaches, lessons become more interesting, meaningful, and understandable for students, while integration helps to master knowledge holistically.

At the same time, as a result of the harmonious use of these two approaches, important skills such as independent thinking, creativity, and the ability to find solutions to problem situations are formed in students. This creates the foundation for their successful activities in future educational stages.

In my opinion, paying special attention to innovation and integration in the primary education process and using them more widely in practice is one of the urgent tasks of today. Because it is at this stage that students' interest in knowledge is formed and a solid foundation is created for their further development

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